

FEATURES OF THE SYSTEM OF MINIMUM CONFRONTATION SITUATIONS FOR ATHLETES AGED 12-14.

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Annatasiya. Futbol, basketbol, voleybol kabi jamoaviy sport turlarida, faoliyat mavzusi bunday mojaroning har bir ishtirokchisi uchun umumiy bo'lganda va bu ishtirokchi faoliyat mavzusini (to'p bilan sport o'yinlarida) faqat (yoki jamoa bilan) o'zlashtirishga intilganda mojaro yuzaga keladi. Tadqiqot shuni ko'rsatdiki, o'rganilgan omillarning, masalan, yosh, qarama-qarshilik vaziyatlarini taqqoslash va ularning o'zaro ta'sirining ta'siri 12-14 yoshda sezilarli bo'ladi; vaziyatlarning murakkabligi oshishi va yoshning pasayishi bilan qaror qabul qilishga sarflanadigan vaqt oshadi; minimal qarama-qarshilik vaziyatlarini tizimlashtirish sifati asosan sportchilarning yoshi va vaziyatlarning statik tuzilishi bilan belgilanadi. 12-14 yoshli sportchilar tomonidan minimal qarama-qarshilik vaziyatlarini tizimlashtirish xususiyatlarini o'rganish natijalari shuni ko'rsatadiki, 12, 13 va 14 yoshli turli xil sportchilarning qarama-qarshilik vaziyatlarini taqqoslash vaqti sportchilarning yoshi ortishi bilan kamayadi. Ko'rsatkichlar hal qilinayotgan qarama-qarshilik vaziyatining turiga bog'liqligi aniqlandi.

Kalit so'zlar: tizimlashtirish, sport zaxirasi, vaziyat, mashg'ulot.

Annotation. In team sports such as football, basketball, volleyball, conflict occurs when the subject of the activity is common to each participant in such a conflict, and this participant seeks solely (or with the team) to master the subject of the activity (in sports games with a ball). The study revealed that the effects of the factors studied, such as age, comparison of situations of confrontation and their interaction, are significant at the age of 12-14 years; with an increase in the complexity of situations and a decrease in age, the time spent on making decisions increases; the quality of systematization of minimal situations of confrontation is largely determined by the age of athletes and the static structure of situations. The results of the study of the characteristics of systematization of minimum situations of confrontation by athletes 12-14 years old show that the time of comparison of situations of confrontation of various types of athletes 12, 13 and 14 years decreases with increasing age of athletes. It was revealed that the indicators depend on the type of the situation of confrontation being solved.

Key words: systematization, sports reserve, situation, training.

Introduction. The most essential characteristics of situational sports (combat sports, individual and team sports) are competitions with opponents, determining winners and recording achievements. In the specialized literature, tactics are widely defined as the art of applying wrestling or combat techniques. However, a structural analysis of tactics allows us to conceptualize it as a complex system of organizing competitive activity, including the athlete's own behavior and the opponent's[1,2,3].

Sports tactics are heterogeneous in their content. This is due to the fact that three characteristic types of competitive conflicts can arise between athletes in different sports, manifesting themselves in different groups of sports. For example, in team sports such as football, basketball, and volleyball, conflict arises when the object of activity is shared by each participant, and each participant strives to acquire control of the object of activity (in sports games, the ball) individually (or as a team). Athletes attempt to exert influence on this object simultaneously. If the desired influence on the ball is not achieved, the participant in the conflict prevents their opponent from doing so.

The complex nature of competitive activity creates constantly changing conditions, necessitating the need to assess the situation and choose actions, usually within a limited timeframe. In this context, a key factor in sport is the athletes' broad arsenal of technical and tactical actions, which contributes to the most effective resolution of competitive situations [4, 6, 7].

In scientific and methodological literature, combat situations are examined from various perspectives. Specifically, they can be viewed as the positioning of athletes at a discrete moment in a fight, or as typical situations. Thus, the general classification of situations leads to a classificatory framework that hinders the variability of technical and tactical actions. Therefore, the importance of systematizing combat situations for young athletes is determined by the need to comprehend and process information in combat conditions. At the same time, given the age differences between athletes in the initial stages and training groups, situations should be minimized.

In our opinion, having achieved a certain level of systematization of minimal confrontation situations at a given age, athletes will be able to overcome more complex structural transformations of technique and tactics that dynamically manifest themselves in competitive activity.

In this regard, the problem of systematization of dynamic situations of confrontation through minimal structural components is relevant.

The purpose of the study was to determine the systematization of minimal combat situations by athletes aged 12-14, taking into account the specifics of the match and the process of solving tactical problems.

Discussion of Results. The testing was conducted to study the systematization of minimal situations by athletes aged 12-14 years old, presented with situations that have meaningful tactical implications (schematic representations of various combat situations).

During testing, three groups (types) of minimal confrontation situations with a high level of opponents' counteraction were used (type 1 is the most difficult, type 2 is less difficult, etc.):

- 1) an attack throughout the ring, as well as special typical situations, which include connecting technical and tactical actions that allow for a quick transition from defense to attack, and are also a continuation of the attack;
- 2) positional attack (attack on half the ring);
- 3) situations in the preliminary phase of the attack.

The identified indicators in minimal combat situations were presented in a specific sequence.

Studies studying the impact of defender activity on strike performance have provided little insight into the specifics of opponents' counterattacks, with the authors primarily focusing on the conditions under which techniques are executed.

Therefore, for a convenient visual assessment, it was proposed to analyze activity through the key performance characteristics.

Low activity is characterized by: no reaction to the technique; passive approach to the attacker; slow arm movements; pointing the arms downward or to the sides; athletes positioned more than 2 meters apart.

Moderate activity is characterized by: passive extension of the arms when blocking strikes; delayed movement toward the operational area; low fighting stance; loss of balance in the defensive stance after repeated stops and jerks; athletes positioned 1 to 2 meters apart.

High activity is characterized by: maintaining a fighting stance after repeated jerks and stops; rapid leg movements; rapid arm movements; simultaneous approach to the opponent; control of the space behind; positioning up to 1 meter apart.

Findings and Conclusion. The developed visual tactical tasks, including interconnected minimal combat situations, are divided into three groups (types) of minimal situations with a high level of opponent resistance: attacks throughout

the ring, as well as special typical situations that include connecting technical and tactical actions that allow for a quick transition from defense to offense, and also serve as a continuation of the attack; positional attacks (attacks on half the ring); and situations in the preliminary phase of the attack.

The refusal to use non-conflict situations (without opponents' counteractions, or passive counteractions) is due, on the one hand, to their low proportion in competitive fights, and on the other, to their lack of meaningful tactical meaning, which would contradict the purpose of organizing and designing our testing.

Minimal confrontation situations allow us to consider technical and tactical activity within the integrated interaction of combat components, which facilitates a comprehensive study of their systematization.

3. The results of a study of the systematization characteristics of minimal confrontation situations by athletes aged 12-14 show that the time it takes athletes aged 12, 13, and 14 to compare different types of confrontation situations decreases with increasing age. It was found that the indicators depend on the type of confrontation situation being resolved.

The effects of the factors studied, including age, comparison of situations, and their interaction, are quite significant, and each of them in most cases exceeds

100 m/sec. Their combined influence accounts for approximately 20-40% of the total decision-making time.

It was found that as the complexity of confrontation situations increases and age decreases, the time spent on decision-making increases. It was also determined that the quality of systematization of minimal confrontation situations is largely determined by the age of the athletes and the static structure of the confrontation situations (type).

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